

Twin Transition Waste Electric and Electronic Equipment Roadmapping Tool to support improvement of environmental sustainability performance of reverse e-waste value chains

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Abstract. The recovery of the huge economic value embedded in waste electric and electronic equipment (WEEE) has been widely discussed through the last years. The activity is relevant also under an environmental point of view, as it enables reduction in the consumption of primary raw materials that are often considered as precious and critical, like rare metals. Nonetheless, few concerns related to the environmental impacts coming from processes, moreover of recycling, of WEEE have been raised. WEEE recycling processes often involve energy intensive activities (e.g., pyrometallurgy) or usage of substances presenting strong acidification potential (e.g., hydrometallurgy). Thus, in this paper is investigated how, under a twin transition perspective, digital technologies can support the offsetting of these environmental impacts. Twin Transition is defined as the synergetic occurrence of green and digital transitions. Furthermore, a novel roadmapping tool, called twin transition WEEE roadmapping tool is proposed. It aims at supporting practitioners of the reverse WEEE value chain in identifying the most useful twin transition implementation pathway, moreover in terms of technology selection, for the contingency of their company.

Keywords: WEEE; Twin Transition, Circular Economy, Roadmapping, Environmental Sustainability.

1 Introduction

In recent times, it has been widely discussed how waste electric and electronic equipment (WEEE) are increasing in quantity year after year [1]. The recovery of metallic and plastics materials contained in WEEE through adequate processes enables retrieval of the great economic value embedded in WEEE [2]. A large share of this economic value comes from the Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) embedded in WEEE [3]. CRMs can be defined in various ways. Typically, they are materials that on the one hand bear a great economic and social value, and on the other bear many risks through their usage (in terms of availability, social impacts, environmental impacts, etc.) [4]–[6]. Policymakers and academicians are paying more and more attention to this topic, moreover

for what concerns the recovery of CRMs embedded in WEEE (e.g., [4], [7]). An emblematic example is the CRMs Act issued by the European Commission, where the objective of sourcing 15% of annual European demand for CRMs from recycling [8].

Nonetheless, it is often argued how recovering secondary metallic from WEEE can bear significant environmental impacts, that should be measured and offset [9]–[11]. Digital technologies can play a crucial role in enabling WEEE recovery and optimizing its performances, including environmental sustainability (ES) [12]–[15], under the paradigm of the so called twin transition (TT). TT is typically defined as the synergetic implementation of Digital Transition and Green Transition, with the former being a lever to implement the latter [16], [17]. Nonetheless, industrial actors usually meet issues and hurdles when trying to implement, often due to a lack of internal competencies and skills in correctly identifying and implementing the correct digital technologies in accordance to their needs and contingency [18], [19]. A significant help can be provided by roadmapping tools, supporting practitioners during their decision-making processes related to the correct selection of digital technologies to be implemented [20], [21]. In this way, companies can enjoy a further support in respecting requests coming from norms and regulations.

Thus, the research objective of this work is understanding how a roadmapping tool may support practitioners in pursuing TT in the sector of WEEE. Thus, the following research question is addressed: how can a roadmapping tool support practitioners in pursuing TT in the sector of the WEEE collection, treatment, and recovery?

According to the authors knowledge, the literature lacks of research where the topic of TT in the WEEE Reverse Value Chain (RVC) is widely analysed. Furthermore, this is the first work where a roadmap for TT specific for WEEE circularity processes is proposed.

The remaining of the paper is structured as follows: in section 2, the adopted methodology is described. In section 3, an overview of the current regulations related to WEEE in Europe is conducted, aiming at showing the relevance of the topic and the direction towards a higher sustainability level that is required. In section 4, a review of the documented applications of digital technologies to the WEEE recovery sector, with the specific aim of improving the ES performance, is conducted, aiming at answering the research question. In section 5, a roadmapping tool supporting WEEE sector practitioners in pursuing TT is proposed. The tool is developed by means of Design Science Research (DSR) methodology. In section 6 the tool is tested through a lab-scale use case. Finally, conclusions are drawn in section 7.

2 Methodology

In this chapter, the methodology adopted to support companies acting in WEEE sector in implementing TT is described.

In [21] by (Perossa et al., 2023), a roadmapping tool, called Twin Transition Cosmetics Roadmapping Tool (TTCRT), focused on the cosmetics industry, was developed

by means of an Action research-based methodology. The aim of the TTCRT is supporting practitioners in developing a TT strategy, moreover in the steps of identification of the right digital technologies to be implemented along the product life cycle, to improve its ES performance. Nonetheless, in the conclusions of [21], it is stated how a possible clue for further research may be the adaptation of the TTCRT to other industrial sectors. The TTCRT is therefore a good starting point for developing an analogous roadmapping tool, focused on WEEE treatment sector.

In order to adapt the TTCRT to WEEE value chain, a twofold review has been conducted: on the one hand, an investigation of the existing European WEEE regulatory framework was performed to understand the current legislative requirements towards companies operating in this sector (section 3). On the other hand, a review of the state of the art of application of digital technologies in the WEEE sector, aiming at improving the environmental sustainability of conducted processes and operations has been performed (section 4). In this way, the relevant peculiarities of the WEEE sector can be analysed and embedded in the new proposed tool.

A further element of analysis has been the identification of the main phases of the WEEE reverse value chain. They have been identified by methodology of literature review and previous knowledge of the authors.

The novel tool is called Twin Transition WEEE Roadmapping Tool (TT-WEEE-RT). It is developed by means of DSR, following the steps proposed by [22]:

- Problem identification and motivation: procedures of recovery of materials and components from WEEE bears non-negligible environmental impacts. TT can offset these impacts, but expertise in this domain is often missing among practitioners.
- Objectives: in this work is proposed the development of a roadmapping tool, called TT-WEEE-RT, to support practitioners of the WEEE sector in pursuing TT for the WEEE circular processes.
- Design and development: the TT-WEEE-RT will be developed by adapting the existing TTCRT to the WEEE sector.
- Demonstration: TT-WEEE-RT will be applied to a lab-scale automated WEEE disassembly process.
- Evaluation: following the demonstration, some evaluations will be performed, supported by the insight provided by the persons in charge of the mentioned process.

3 Review of European WEEE regulatory framework

Several actions and legislations have been put in place by the European Commission in the last decade to improving rate of return of WEEE and supporting efficient reuse of secondary resources, improving the environmental performance of electric and electronic equipment (EEE) sector (e.g.: [23]–[25]). They are relevant as they highlight the main trends and key points of WEEE and their treatment. The main regulative reference

for WEEE in EU is [25]. It embeds the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) principle presented in the waste framework directive [26]. [25] applies to six categories of WEEE: (i) temperature exchange equipment, (ii) Screens, monitors, and equipment containing screens having a surface greater than 100 cm², (iii) Lamps, (iv) Large equipment (any external dimension more than 50 cm), (v) Small equipment (no external dimension more than 50 cm), (vi) Small IT and telecommunication equipment (no external dimension more than 50 cm). Among the WEEE not included in the list there are means of transport for persons or goods. [25] aims at minimizing WEEE disposal into unsorted municipal waste, setting targets for e-waste collection rate for member states (65% of total EEE placed in the market in the previous three years or 85% of total WEEE generated in the year). It also encourages EEE producers to meet minimum WEEE treatment targets, and encourages cooperation between producers and recyclers to design EEE in line with EU ErP directive [27]. Another crucial document is the RoHS Directive [28]. It targets the usage of materials that can be harmful for humans and environment in EEE once they become WEEE. Ten substances among heavy metals, flame retardants, and plasticizers are identified as hazardous and their usage regulated. The ErP Directive [27] targets over 40 product categories, including several EEEs. [27] addresses eco-design requirements covering the entire product life cycle. All these Directives witness the willingness of stimulating circularity of the WEEE by the EU.

Further standards have been developed by the Comité européen de normalisation en électronique et en électrotechnique (CENEC), with EN 4555X series. In particular, relevant for CE of WEEE, there are: (i) EN 4552:2020 ‘General method for the assessment of durability of energy related products’; (ii) EN 4553:2020 ‘General method for the assessment of the ability to remanufacture energy-related products; (iii) EN 4554:2020 ‘General methods for the assessment of the ability to repair, reuse and upgrade energy-related products’; (iv) EN 4555:2019 ‘General methods for assessing the recyclability and recoverability of energy-related products’; (v) EN 4556:2019 ‘General method for assessing the proportion of reused components in energy related products; (vi) EN 4557:2020 ‘General method for assessing the proportion of recycled material content in energy-related products’. These standards are symptomatic of a strong need by stakeholders of evaluating circularity of EEEs and WEEEs and, thus, of a strong demand of more circular and more sustainable WEEE. Further relevant standards by the CENEC are EN 50625-1:2014 and EN 50614:2020. They cover collection, transport, re-use, and treatment of WEEE. They concern depollution and its monitoring, monitoring of downstream treatment, and aim at ensuring uniformity in auditing.

4 Review of the potential applications of digital technologies for WEEE treatment

Under the perspective of the TT, several digital technologies are addressed in the literature for being used in optimizing ES of circular practices related to WEEE.

Tracing technologies may perform a crucial role in uncovering information of state and conditions of components that are found in WEEE, and potentially also of the materials embedded in them. In this way, it is possible to select those components that can be reused instead of being recycled, saving the environmental impacts related to the recycling process [12]. Obviously, in this kind of information sharing, cloud computing technology has a vital enabling role [29]. At the same time, a crucial tool for gathering this kind of data in a circular value chain context is the Internet of Things [30].

Usage of automated robots to perform disassembly operations allows performing pre-treatment avoiding the risk for human operators to get in contact with hazardous materials potentially embedded in WEEE [15]. Artificial Intelligence algorithms are key enablers for managing and optimising automated disassembly processes [31].

An other relevant role is played by simulation techniques to optimize the ES performance of reverse supply chains and treatment of WEEE. In [14] is provided an example using artificial intelligence-based genetic algorithms for simulation aiming at economic and environmental optimization of WEEE reverse supply chain in Sao Paulo. Another example can be found in [32], where digital twin-based simulation techniques are used to optimize the energy efficiency of a lab-scale smartphone disassembly line. Digital twin is stated in [33] to have contributed to optimising, under an energy efficiency point of view, the refining process of recovered copper. In [32] it is also explored how virtual reality can act in synergy with digital twin technology, enhancing the human-simulation interface. In [34] is discussed how process simulation can be applied to quantify resource efficiency and overall environmental performance of e-waste recycling.

Augmented reality is considered in [35] as a tool providing easy-to-read real-time feedback related to recycling processes, to help improvement in resource optimisation. A further technology finding extensive applications in WEEE treatment is additive manufacturing. It can be used, indeed, to produce printed electronics starting from recycled materials [36]. Additive manufacturing is considered as a technology that significantly improves the materials efficiency in manufacturing starting from recycled materials, if compared to traditional machining processes [37].

5 The Twin Transition WEEE Roadmapping Tool

The support that digital technologies provide to improving the ES performance of circularity practices referred to WEEE is well documented, as described in section 3.

Thus, given what already mentioned in the previous chapters, an adaptation of the TTCRT to the WEEE sector is proposed here.

5.1 Structure of the TT-WEEE-RT

Like the TTCRT, the TT-WEEE-RT will be conceived to be applied to one product per time. In the context of WEEE, as a product, is meant a given typology of waste, or

components that undergoes a series of treatments. The main structure of the TT-WEEE-RT is the same of the TTCRT, divided into three main sections:

- **Know-why:** in this section, the main targets and drivers of the company towards sustainability are identified through a questionnaire submitted to the persons working in the enterprise. Identified objectives and drivers will work as a compass in the implementation of the technologies to be implemented.
- **Know-what:** in this section, it is evaluated, along the steps of the considered process, what is the current level of ES performance for the considered product, according to some identified performance dimensions. The purpose of this section is identifying the main points of strength and weakness of the considered circularity procedures in terms of ES.
- **Know-how:** in this section, it is assessed the current level of digital technologies in place, considering only those that have a positive direct or indirect impact on ES. The goal here is defining in which areas TT implementation is more developed and in which areas it is less.

As in the TTCRT, the filling of the listed three sections constitutes the assessment phase, where the current situation of the considered processes is depicted. Basing on the results of this assessment, is performed the roadmapping phase, where it is defined what are the next technological implementations useful to be performed.

While the TTCRT, in the know-what and know-how phases, considers the life cycle of a cosmetic product, the TT-WEEE-RT needs to consider the possible phases of a WEEE RVC. The proposed phases to be considered are the following:

- **Collection phase:** when the WEEE are collected and sorted and, through reverse logistics channels, are sent to disassembly and recycling plants [38].
- **Pre-treatment phase:** when the various components are separated, so that they can be reused, remanufactured, or their materials recycled in the subsequent phases, or where mechanical processes like shredding or crushing are used for WEEE size reduction [39], [40].
- **Remanufacturing or refurbishing:** in this phase, the components that can be entirely recovered are remanufactured or refurbished for further usage [41].
- **Materials recovery:** for those components that can be recovered, they are sent to recycling plants where the materials embedded in them can be recovered [42].
- **Materials refining:** to improve the quality of the recovered materials, it is often necessary to refine them [43].
- **Production of new EEEs from secondary materials** [36].

This list of steps was tested by an academic expert in the field. In some cases, some of the phases can be not covered in the analysis. This depends on the defined boundaries of the analysis. Furthermore, some routes are alternative to others for specific components or materials (e.g., if a component is sent to materials recovery phase, it shall not be sent to remanufacturing phase).

The dimensions of assessment of the ES performance in the know-what and know-how phases are also changed from the TTCRT, to be adapted to the WEEE context. For this reason, the dimensions of ES to be considered have been inspired to the results of the review conducted in section 3 about the possible applications of digital technologies to WEEE industry. The selected dimensions are the following:

- Improved evaluation of components to identify the most appropriate route minimising environmental impacts [12], [29], [30] (reusage is less impacting than remanufacturing and refurbishing, which are less impacting than recycling [48]).
- Minimization of risk on human health due to contact with hazardous materials embedded in WEEE [15].
- Maximization of the materials efficiency [34], [37].
- Maximization of energy efficiency [32], [33].

In the know-how section, are listed the digital technologies to be considered for TT in the WEEE context, as emerged from the review described in section 3:

- Tracing technologies [12].
- Internet of Things [30].
- Automated and collaborative robots [15].
- Data analytics and artificial intelligence [14], [31].
- Simulation technologies [14], [32]–[34].
- Augmented reality and Virtual reality [32], [35].
- Additive manufacturing [36].

Some of the listed technologies can be implemented also as a support to the other technologies. A scheme representing the TT-WEEE-RT is provided in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the TT-WEEE-RT adapted from [21]

On the other hand, the know-how section is structured as shown in Figure 2:

Digital Technologies	WEEE Treatment and Recovery processes phases						
	TT-WEEE-RT	Collection Phase	Pre-treatment Phase	Remanufacturing or Refurbishing Phase	Materials recovery Phase	Materials Refining Phase	Production of new EEEs Phase
Tracing technologies							
Internet of Things							
Automated and Collaborative Robots							
Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence							
Simulation Technologies							
Augmented reality and Virtual reality							
Additive manufacturing							

Fig. 2. Scheme of the know-how section of the TT-WEEE-RT

The know-what section can be compiled according to the following scale, which is similar to the one proposed in [21], that was adapted from [44]–[46]:

- Not applicable (level X): it is outside study boundaries, or it is not possible to apply the considered technology to the considered context.
- No strategy (Level 0): actions are not taken or are exclusively driven by the need to be compliant with laws and regulations. No targets are defined.
- Defensive strategy (Level 1): actions with positive impacts on ES are in place but they focus on risk and cost reduction. Mainly the economic dimension is considered. Environmental targets are not defined.

- Accomodative strategy (Level 2): actions are taken considering ES performance and are mainly market driven. Targets are clear but conservative and processes are partially monitored.
- Proactive strategy (Level 3): actions are taken considering ES performance. The company continuously seeks to integrate the sustainability vision by anticipating market requests. Targets are ambitious and processes are continuously monitored.

For filling the know-how table, the following scale was developed. It is similar to the one proposed in [21], which was adapted from [47]:

- Level X: the technology is not applicable in the considered context.
- Level 0: there is no implementation of that technology in the considered RVC phase or its implementation does not consider ES.
- Level 1: pilot actions are in place to implement that technology in the considered phase of the RVC or, alternatively, the technology is well implemented but with no ES objectives. Nonetheless, there are collateral ES benefits resulting from the implementation.
- Level 2: implementation of the technology in that stage of RVC is initiated and ES benefits are observable. Alternatively, the technology is well implemented for other primary purposes, but conscious secondary aspects related ES improvements are enjoyed and measured.
- Level 3: Advanced and mature implementation of the technology in that RVC stage mainly for ES purposes are in place, resulting in clear and measured benefits.

6 Test and evaluation

The TT-WEEE-RT has been tested by being applied to a lab-scale disassembly process of printed circuit boards (PCBs) at the Industry 4.0 Lab “Marco Garetti” of Politecnico di Milano. The process is performed with a Cobot and integrates artificial intelligence for image recognition. Through image recognition, it is possible to automatically identify components over the PCBs that are valuable and reusable. Then, the cobot can detach them from the PCB itself. The process is one stage of a three-stages lab-scale macro-process for recovery of materials from WEEE, developed in the context of the Horizon Europe 2020 Research and Innovation Action called TREASURE, co-funded by the European Commission.

The first step of the application of the TT-WEEE-RT led to submit a questionnaire to the researchers working on the process. The main outcomes of the questionnaire led to defining the following objectives and drivers as crucial:

- As external drivers: (i) increase in the demand for scarce resources; (ii) tackling the issue of climate change and environmental pollution; (iii) anticipating ever more stringent rules at national and international levels.

- As internal drivers: (i) willingness to introduce technologies able to optimize ES performances; (ii) availability to hire qualified human resources to optimize the ES performance.

The filling of the know-what and know-why sections was limited to the disassembly process, which takes place in the Lab. Results are illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

	TT-WEEE-RT	Disassembly Phase
Environmental sustainability performances	Improved components evaluation	3
	Minimization of risks for human health	3
	Maximization of materials efficiency	1
	Maximization of energy efficiency	0

Fig. 3. Application of the know-what phase

The Lab-scale process is able to provide state-of-the-art components evaluation, with the explicit aim of sending to the more sustainable routes (reusage or remanufacturing) the components for whom this is feasible. Explicit targets are present under this perspective. Furthermore, the automated nature of the process leads to totally avoiding any type of direct contact between operators and eventual hazardous materials. Considering the materials efficiency, the process considers it, and actions are performed to improve it, but targets are focusing exclusively on economic returns coming from this efficiency. Furthermore, the process is not able yet to recover all the typologies of potentially valuable components. Finally, actions for maximisation of energy efficiency are totally neglected, even though the energy consumption levels of a cobot are typically not high according to the operators of the Lab .

	TT-WEEE-RT	Disassembly Phase
Digital Technologies	Tracing technologies	0
	Internet of Things	0
	Automated and Collaborative Robots	3
	Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence	3
	Simulation Technologies	0
	Augmented reality and Virtual reality	0
	Additive manufacturing	X

Fig. 4. Application of the know-how phase

The only technologies in place are currently collaborative robots and artificial intelligence. They are present at a state-of-the-art level of implementation, and both of them are actively focused on environmental sustainability targets. There is a complete lack of focus on the other considerable technologies.

Concerning the roadmapping phase, the following main points have been addressed:

- Initialization of tracing technologies implementation, in collaboration with partners sending the PCBs to the disassembly process and receiving the components from it, may further support components evaluation.
- Implementation of Internet of Things technologies for smart measurement of the process performances can be a first step for dealing with materials and energy efficiency. Nonetheless, this is deemed by the operators in the lab as being more useful when the process will have a higher technology readiness level.
- Implementation of simulation technologies to better evaluate and optimize environmental sustainability parameters of the disassembly process has been deemed by the Lab operators as a useful and feasible possibility. Nonetheless, according to the operators in the Lab, the Technology Readiness Level of the process is still too low for having useful results from Implementing simulation, according to Lab operators.
- Finally, Augmented reality and Virtual reality have been deemed as unuseful for a so low technology readiness level.

After the testing, the TT-WEEE-RT has been evaluated through an interview to the Lab operators. They stated that the objective of the tool of defining the useful possible implementations under a TT perspective is clearly satisfied. Nonetheless, they complained how the tool does not provide an automated mechanism for the selection of the technologies to be implemented, and in the roadmapping phase a lot of work is left to the human effort and interpretation.

7 Conclusions and future research

This work tackled the problem of the environmental impacts coming from the circular practices in the WEEE sector. In order to offset these emissions, the solutions provided by the TT pathway are explored. In a first review, the current trends in terms of regulations and legislations of WEEE are analysed, to understand the direction the sector is taking. In a second review, the potentials of the digital technologies in terms of TT applications for WEEE are analysed. It emerged that environmental sustainability performance can be supported by digital technologies moreover in terms of improvement of the reverse routes selection (recycling, remanufacturing, reuse) of the components and materials according to their condition. This enables the selection of environmentally more sustainable routes, according to [48]. A further important element is the

minimisation of risks for human health via automation, preventing operators from getting in touch with hazardous materials. Furthermore, it emerged that materials and energy efficiency can both be optimised through digital technologies correct implementation. Subsequently, to support companies in facing the hurdles they typically face when pursuing TT, a roadmapping tool tailored for WEEE sector is proposed. The tool is named TT-WEEE-RT. Finally, a testing of the tool in a lab-scale environment is conducted.

The work presents few limitations. First of all, the test, by taking place in a lab-scale environment, limits the possibility of application of the tool. Indeed, the only phase of the WEEE reverse value chain (RVC) that can be considered is the disassembly. Furthermore, the possible evaluations that can emerge from the roadmapping phase are limited by the research-oriented environment where the test takes place.

Cues for future research may include two main possibilities. First, as emerged during the evaluation phase, it would be interesting to modify the roadmapping phase of the tool to make the evaluations more automatic, relying less on human opinions and subjectivity. Furthermore, given the adaptability that the TTCRT, conceived for the cosmetics industry, has proved to have in this work in being adapted to different industries and contexts, it would be interesting trying to adapt this typology of tool to further sectors, supporting TT in other industries too.

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